

THE CONCEPT OF DELEGATED LAW-MAKING AND GUARANTEES OF ITS EXECUTION

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Abstract: In this scientific article, the concept and features of delegated law-making will be considered. It should be noted that at the moment this legal category is the object of ambiguous discussions, discussions, scientific papers. In science, there are many opinions about its necessity and the properties of its application. Often, delegated law-making becomes very much in demand in practice when the highest representative body, concentrating legislative power in itself, cannot provide for absolutely all spheres of society and the state. Here there is a reason why it is necessary to delegate law-making powers to responsible state bodies. The development of legal and theoretical foundations of delegated law-making at the moment seems very relevant, which predetermined the existence of this study.

Keywords: lawmaking, delegated, authority, guarantees, legal science, subject, state body.

In legal science, there are many definitions of delegated law-making, which are associated with certain features and criteria of the field of activity of state bodies under study.

According to many scientists, delegated law-making is the publication of a normative legal act on the authority granted, acting for a certain time or without specifying the terms, proceeding from the law, or on direct instructions from one (higher) state body to another (lower) while maintaining a certain system of control by a higher authority over the implementation of delegated powers, as a result, there is a temporary expansion of the powers of the body to which they are delegated.

At the same time, delegation means the granting of authority, its distribution among government agencies and civil servants of various levels. It should be noted that this is a very popular function in the implementation and distribution of the functions of state power. This is the empowerment of one structure of the highest authority – another structure that is lower in level than the first. The acts that this power structure will adopt will be considered subordinate and created in compliance with laws and subordinate acts of the highest level (decrees, resolutions of the President, Cabinet of Ministers, etc.).

The essence of delegated law-making is that one subject of law-making transfers part of its rule-making competence to another subject of law-making, and then the subject with additional powers publishes sources of law on such issues.

One of the main goals of delegated law—making is to accelerate the law-making process. Initially, it was for this purpose that the parliaments of European states transferred part of their powers to the government. This is how the concept of "delegated lawmaking" appeared. Today delegated lawmaking is actively carried out by governments (France, Italy, Spain, Poland, etc.) and heads of state (Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan). The acts issued by them actually have the force of law.

Delegated law-making is understood as "the activities of state bodies, officials and certain non-governmental organizations and institutions related to the adoption of regulations on the basis of the transfer to them of the relevant right of bodies and persons directly authorized for such activities."

V. M. Shamarov understands delegated law-making as law-making carried out on behalf, i.e. by transferring their law-making powers from one subject of law-making to another subject.

We consider it necessary to note that in the modern legal literature devoted to the problems of law-making, not enough attention is paid to such a method of law-making as delegated, compared with direct and authorized. When describing delegated law-making, the authors usually pay attention only to the concept and historical background of this phenomenon, without affecting the state and trends of this method of law-making in the field of modern legal regulation, which determines the relevance of this issue.

Speaking about the issue we are considering, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "delegated" and "authorized" law-making. If delegated law-making is understood as "the activities of state bodies and/or officials, as well as individual non-governmental organizations related to the adoption of regulatory legal acts on the basis of an order (delegation) of another body or official", then authorized - "the approval of norms by state bodies that have developed independently of them, in the form of a custom (business habit), or developed by non-governmental organizations", which can "be carried out both before the adoption of an act - by approving a future legal act, and after the adoption of such an act by giving consent to its application."

Thus, the term "authorization" should be considered as the approval of something by the highest authority, and "delegation" - as the permission of law-

making activities to other subjects of law-making on the basis of the act of delegation.

We agree with the opinion of N. V. Inochkina that "the delegation of law-making powers allows for some optimization of public administration, contributes to the rational distribution of working time, helps to establish the practice of training highly qualified personnel."

The reasons for delegating law-making powers are quite diverse. But it is definitely necessary to take into account the aspect that delegation at the moment is a great way to distribute the workload for the implementation of a very responsible social task – the creation of a rule of law, bringing it to society and its correct interpretation.

According to S.G. Dzybova, the reasons for delegation are "the increasing complexity of modern society; the workload of the legislative body, lack of time, lack of necessary mechanisms for the implementation of law-making functions."

The value of delegated lawmaking also lies in the fact that through its mechanisms in a globalizing world, national legislation can be adjusted (without limiting the sovereignty of the state) in accordance with the modification of international legal standards.

As for the guarantees of the performance of delegated law-making, the following guarantees should be highlighted in this part:

- legality, i.e. creation of normative acts in compliance with the Constitution and laws;
- legal basis of activity: delegated will be only the law-making that has been transferred to a lower-level state body or official in accordance with the established procedure;
- professionalism, which is expressed in the work on the adoption of laws, which should be carried out on an ongoing basis with the involvement of scientists and specialists, with the conduct of scientific examinations of draft laws;
- constant work on forecasting of normative activity , monitoring of the work of subordinate bodies by higher;
- efficiency (timeliness of the issuance of regulations);
- reliance on the achievements of legal science;
- constant interaction with other state bodies, activation of the work of the state mechanism.

It should be noted that the guarantee of the performance of delegated law-making is based on the conditions created by the state for the implementation of rule-making activities by authorized entities.

Thus, we have listed the main, in our opinion, guarantees and we consider it necessary to note that this list is not closed. Some of these guarantees have their own difficulties in practice, which gives science a reason not only to study their patterns, but also to supplement the law with an adequate response to these problems.

The effectiveness of the delegation of law-making powers will be ensured when the clearly defined duties and responsibilities of the authority for their non-fulfillment, the reporting procedure of the authority on the exercise of delegated powers are worked out at the legislative level, as well as the conditions and procedure for terminating the exercise of delegated powers are clearly spelled out.

Taking into account the above positions on the definition of delegated rule-making, it would be advisable to define delegated rule-making, in particular, is the activity of state bodies, officials associated with the adoption of normative legal acts on the basis of the transfer of appropriate powers to them for such activities by higher competent authorities.

The social necessity and practical benefits of delegating law-making powers from the central (higher) state executive authorities are obvious. Their legal definition and understanding depends on the reasons for delegation in the general legal sense. And in every state, especially in the Republic of Uzbekistan, delegating the largest amount of authority to create regulations is a progressive area of work that needs to be constantly worked on.

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